

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KAFERE****FIRST NAME: CHANCELAR****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did use Turabian in-text references

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 11)

List 5 to 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Academic essay writing process (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7–12)
2. Academic essay structure (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 10–11)
3. Punctuations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15–23)
4. American vs British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24–32)
5. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33–39)

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ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have successfully studied the recommended material for the first period of the ACA-401D course. Adeptness at academic essay writing is one of the fundamental skills for academic and professional success. Unlike other forms of writing, this is formal and follows strict rules in format and language. Hence, enhancing proficiency in academic essay writing is imperative for doctoral-level studies.

In this response paper, I discuss key concepts I have learned, which include the essay writing process, general essay structure, correct use of punctuation, and plagiarism and its associated effects. In addition, I will briefly discuss the use of British and American English in academic writing and an overall comment on my perception of the whole study period.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING PROCESS

The academic essay writing process has common basic steps, including defining the topic, researching the subject, creating an outline, and writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma

2024, 7–12). The effort invested in each step varies with the writer, essay topic, and type of academic essay. Following logical steps in their correct sequence makes writing easier and improves output.

Since academic essay writing addresses a question, the first critical step is defining the question and understanding the writing task (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7). The question or hypothesis guides the essay's aims and the evidence necessary to support the arguments. At this point, it is essential to determine the intended audience as this determines the approach to take, the level of detail, and the language, such as using technical jargon. Researching the topic follows as the next step to gather relevant available information about the topic upon which arguments will be based. The author can systematically review existing literature on the topic to gather information. This stage includes creative and critical thinking to evaluate the information and decide on the material to support the arguments.

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After defining and gathering information, the next step would be to organize the ideas into a logical plan (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 9). This plan guides the writing process and helps keep it organized by filtering information relevant to addressing the topic and laying down important ideas and evidence to support them. Once a rough sketch is available, the author can develop the first draft.

Essays go through the editing process before finalization. It is advisable to review the draft essay a few days after the initial draft with a fresh mind to identify areas of improvement in structure and content (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11–12). The author can verify whether the essay meets the prescribed format and referencing requirements and whether it adequately answers the question.

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3) ACADEMIC ESSAY STRUCTURE

Academic essays must generally follow a clear structure and format, including an introduction, body, and conclusion (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 10). The introduction provides a broader background to the topic and narrows it down to a specific theme, highlights the question, and briefly summarises the essay. All details and arguments are covered in the essay body and should be presented clearly and logically. This section must be organized into paragraphs, each addressing a separate issue but logically linked. Paragraphs should, in turn, conform to a defined structure, which includes a topic sentence, supporting sentences, evidence, analysis, and a concluding sentence (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11). The academic essay conclusion is the last part, which should occupy only one paragraph. In contrast to the introduction, the conclusion develops from specific to broad by stating the answer and summarizing the key points to remind the readers how the author reached the answer. Although I was familiar with the essay structure, I got to understand it better during this period.

4) PUNCTUATIONS

Correct punctuation is essential in academic essays to ensure that the intended meaning is conveyed to the reader(s) clearly. Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024, 16-23) recommend minimum use of punctuation marks as much as practically possible and using them only where they are necessary. The authors clearly explained the use of essential punctuation marks with clear examples, making everything understandable. Although I knew the use of most of them, I learned new things that appeared simple but needed to be done correctly, such as placing of a full stop when using bullet points. It is difficult to remember all the punctuations and their rules of use. Therefore, I will refer to the relevant section of the Coursepack when necessary, and with time, I will get to know and remember all.

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5) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

Although they are mainly similar, British and American English have differences that should be considered (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25–32). This part was an eye-opener for me as I often unknowingly mixed the two types of English in writing and talking. For academic essay writing, one has to choose one of the two English forms and apply it consistently. Some words differ only in pronunciation, which is not essential for writing as the spelling remains the same. Some words have the same pronunciation, but spelling differs between British and American English. Other differences are in grammar, punctuation, the meaning of certain words, and different everyday usage variations. Authors should pay careful attention when writing and editing the document, and they can effectively do this by setting the desired proofing language in Microsoft Word.

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6) PLAGIARISM

Correct and adequate citing of sources of information consulted during the essay writing process is paramount (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34–39). Citing helps to avoid plagiarism, a phenomenon whereby one takes work from other authors and presents it as their own. I was astonished to learn that contrary to what I believed, plagiarism takes different forms depending on the context and can be intentional or unintentional. It includes taking words from a source without quotation marks and referencing and taking ideas even presented in one's own words without acknowledging the source. Authors cannot reuse their work without proper referencing, constituting self-plagiarism (Masic 2012, 210).

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Paraphrasing is an indispensable skill for academic essay writing, which all students must master. Direct quotes from the text must be limited to cases where it is essential. For any good essay, correct in-text referencing following the stipulated referencing style for the type of paper is a prerequisite.

7) CONCLUSION

Academic essays must conform to set standard formats, styles, and other requirements as applicable, depending on their nature. Through this module, I now understand better the process of writing an academic essay, proper structure to follow, appropriate language use, and ways of avoiding plagiarism by correct referencing. I had the opportunity to put the knowledge to immediate use in writing this essay and will build on it to improve my writing skills continually. The content of the entire period was an excellent foundation to start my studies, which involve a lot of academic writing, an area where I need improvement.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press.

Masic, Izet. 2012. "Plagiarism in Scientific Publishing." *Acta Informatica Medica* 20 (no. 4): 208–13. <https://doi.org/10.5455/aim.2012.20.208-213>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

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